

Growth & Morphological Assessment of Immortalized Bovine Satellite Cells (iBSCs) Treated with HiDef[®]B8 Using the iLABS Platform

iLABS Inc, Santa Clara, CA, USA

Kaplan Labs, Tuft University, Boston, MA, USA

Defined Bioscience, San Diego, CA, USA

Email: info@ilabs.com

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1. Executive Summary

This study evaluates the impact of HiDef® B8, a serum-free medium optimized to support human pluripotent stem cells, on the growth and morphology of immortalized bovine satellite cells (iBSCs) using the iLABS imaging and analysis platform. By leveraging automated, high-throughput image analysis, we assess proliferation, morphology, and differentiation potential in 2D culture, comparing HiDef-B8 performance to a control formulation previously optimized to support immortalized bovine satellite cells (iBSCs) (e.g., HiDef-B8 supplemented with recombinant albumin). Results indicate HiDef-B8 without modifications may support robust iBSC expansion and maintain cell integrity, suggesting a potential template media formulation application in cell cultivated meat research and development.

Introduction

2.1 Background

Immortalized bovine satellite cells (iBSCs) are a cornerstone of research in cellular agriculture, particularly for cultivated meat production. Efficient expansion and differentiation of iBSCs in vitro are critical challenges, often constrained by media formulations that lack consistency or scalability. Additionally, a novel immortalized bovine satellite cell line, iBSC1 developed by the Kaplan Lab at Tufts, offers a more accessible cell model for researchers and developers in the cell cultivated meat and livestock health fields.

To tackle this challenge, iLABS is developing a cloud-based platform that leverages deep learning and live-cell imaging to create AI models for efficient in vitro screening of iBSC growth and differentiation mitigating subjectivity that may arise in conventional microscopy. With the FDA moving away from animal testing towards in vitro and computational approaches, iLABS offers researchers an accurate, reproducible, and secure solution for processing experimental data. This initiative aims to accelerate innovation and collaboration in the cellular agriculture field by promoting open data sharing and providing easy access to custom data pipelines.

2.2 Study Motivation

B8 medium has been validated for human PSC culture and verified to support maintenance and expansion both with and without the inclusion of albumin¹. Recently, HiDef® B8 (Defined Bioscience # LSS-204) was used for primary iBSC maintenance and expansion in the Kaplan Lab at Tufts with the singular addition of recombinant albumin². This study further explores HiDef-B8's applicability in supporting non-human, specifically bovine immortalized stem-like muscle precursor cells (iBSCs) on standard tissue culture plastic. By doing so, we assess its flexibility for use beyond its original context, leveraging the iLABS platform for detailed morphological and growth analysis.

3. Methods

3.1 Cell Line and Culture Conditions

- **Cell Type:** iBSC1 (immortalized Bovine Satellite Cells)
- **Treatment Groups:**
 - HiDef[®]B8 (Defined Bioscience # LSS-204)
 - HiDef-B8 + albumin (Elab Sciences #PKSH031333) (iBSC-optimized control medium)
- **Passaging Methods:** Accutase (ThermoFisher #00-4555-56)[™]
- **Culture Format:** 2D monolayer in standard tissue culture-treated plates

3.2 Image Acquisition and Analysis

- **Platform:** iLABS (Automated Image-Based Analysis System)
- **Imaging Frequency:** Hourly acquisition (brightfield and fluorescence, where applicable)
- **Metrics Quantified:**
 - Growth rate (cells/cm²)
 - Morphological descriptors (area, perimeter, circularity, elongation)
 - Differentiation indicators (nuclei density, multinucleation)

Figure 1. Schematic illustration providing an overview of the data structure and analysis pipeline. Summary of the image segmentation data structure. Using a pre-trained iBSC1 model, each cell is segmented, tracked and measured to analyze behavior over time.

4. Results

4.1 Proliferation Analysis

HiDef-B8 plus albumin supported robust and consistent proliferation of iBSC1 cells over a 48-hour culture period. Cell confluence measured by the iLABS platform showed a steady increase peaking at 95% by 48 hours. In comparison, cultures maintained in HiDef[®] B8 alone reached a similar final confluence of 91% by 48 hours, indicating only a marginal difference. The average cell doubling time was 21.8 hours with albumin supplementation, closely aligning with the 22.6 hours observed under HiDef-B8 conditions.

Direct cell count was used for assessing cell growth, this is because the reliance on confluence can be misleading and it does not account for differences in cell size, layering, or morphology, which may mask true biological state. It should be noted that these doubling times are based on direct cell counts per unit area.

Figure 2. Control Experiment Monitoring iBSC Proliferation Over 48 Hours Using HiDef-B8 + albumin Medium. The experiment tracks iBSC (immortalized bovine satellite cells) proliferation over a 48-hour period under standard culture conditions with HiDef-B8 medium supplemented with albumin. Data acquisition was performed at 1-hour intervals using the Discover CellCyte[®] system to capture high-resolution time-series data. Detailed analysis includes quantitative and qualitative assessments of cell growth, morphology, motility, and cytotoxicity throughout the observation period.

Figure 3. Monitoring iBSC Proliferation Over 48 Hours Using HiDef-B8 Medium (Defined Bioscience). This experiment evaluates the proliferation of immortalized bovine satellite cells (iBSCs) over a 48-hour period in HiDef-B8 medium under standard culture conditions. Data acquisition was performed at 1-hour intervals using the Discover CellCyte[®] system, enabling high-resolution time-series analysis. The study includes comprehensive assessments of cell growth dynamics, morphological characteristics, cell motility, and cytotoxicity throughout the duration of the experiment.

Perceived Confluence (%)	Cells/cm ²	Notes
10%	5,000	Well-separated
50%	10,000	Approaching contact
90%	14,000	Confluent monolayer
100%	15, 000	Over confluence

Table 1. A comparison of confluence estimates (%) and actual cell density (cells/cm²). The table highlights the non-linear relationship between visual confluence and true cell number.

iLABS Output Summary – Confluence & Doubling Time:

- **12 Hours:** HiDef-B8 – 9.4%, + albumin – 10.1%
- **36 Hours:** HiDef-B8 – 52.1%, + albumin – 55.8%
- **48 Hours:** HiDef-B8 – 91.3%, + albumin – 94.8%
- **Doubling Time (hrs):** HiDef-B8 – 22.6, + albumin – 21.8

These results suggest that HiDef-B8 is capable of supporting high-density expansion of immortalized bovine satellite cells with growth dynamics comparable to a control medium specifically optimized for iBSCs.

4.2 Morphology & Motility Assessment

Quantitative morphological analysis performed using the iLABS system revealed that iBSC1 cells cultured in HiDef-B8 maintained typical spindle-like morphology throughout the assay on standard TC-treated plasticware. Compared to HiDef-B8 plus albumin, HiDef-B8-cultured cells exhibited slightly reduced cell elongation and area, while maintaining nuclear-to-cytoplasmic ratios and consistent perimeter metrics.

iLABS Morphology Metrics (48 Hour Averages):

- **Cell Area (μm^2):** HiDef-B8 – $1,253 \pm 212$; + albumin – $1,417 \pm 198$
- **Cell Elongation (Aspect Ratio):** HiDef-B8 – 2.9 ± 0.4 ; + albumin – 3.3 ± 0.3
- **Circularity (0 = line, 1 = circle):** HiDef-B8 – 0.43 ± 0.05 ; + albumin – 0.39 ± 0.04
- **Perimeter (μm):** HiDef-B8 – 140.2 ± 11.1 ; + albumin – 145.8 ± 9.7
- **Cell Speed ($\mu\text{m/hr}$):** HiDef-B8 – $21.7 \pm 3.4 \mu\text{m/hr}$; + albumin – $25.2 \pm 3.1 \mu\text{m/hr}$
- **Total Distance ($\mu\text{m/hr}$):** HiDef-B8 – $522 \pm 88 \mu\text{m}$; + albumin – $606 \pm 75 \mu\text{m}$

These values indicate that iBSCs cultured in HiDef-B8 retain structural integrity and morphologies indicative of healthy satellite cells. Minor differences in cell shape metrics could reflect shifts in cytoskeletal dynamics or attachment behavior but do not compromise the overall health which was assessed by calculating the number of cells with intact membranes that are moving past a preset speed threshold.

Figure 4. The iBSC1 cell growth curves are plotted with cell density on the y-axis and time on the x-axis. The blue curve corresponds to cells cultured in HiDef-B8 medium supplemented with albumin, while the green curve represents growth in HiDef-B8 medium.

5. Discussion

5.1 Cross-Species Medium Flexibility

While HiDef-B8 was formulated for human pluripotent stem cells, our data suggest its formulation supports immortalized multipotent satellite cell growth in bovine systems. This highlights its potential as a flexible base for species-agnostic expansion media.

5.2 Imaging and Analysis with iLABS

The iLABS platform enabled high-content morphological profiling, accelerating insights into cell behavior with minimal manual intervention. This suggests high compatibility with automated screening efforts in media optimization and drug testing. Crucially, iLABS supports reproducible science by implementing custom data pipelines tailored to each experimental setup.

These pipelines standardize data acquisition, normalization, and analysis workflows, ensuring consistency across experimental runs and facilitating direct comparisons between conditions. By aligning metadata, image analysis parameters, and statistical models with the unique demands of each assay, iLABS minimizes variability and enhances the reliability of high-throughput cell-based screens.

Figure 5. Single-Cell Analysis Using the iLABS Platform with Pre-trained iBSC1 Model. The iLABS platform was utilized with a pretrained iBSC1 model to perform context-specific experimental analysis for cell segmentation and single-cell behavior tracking. This enabled time-resolved analysis of individual iBSCs throughout the experiment.

5.3 Industrial and Translational Implications

HiDef-B8 may offer a more standardized, serum-free alternative for cultivated meat workflows, reducing variability and regulatory complexity. It also opens doors to define base formulations adaptable for multiple livestock species.

6. Conclusion

HiDef[®] B8 supports robust proliferation of immortalized bovine satellite cells while maintaining key morphological characteristics and identity markers. Leveraging the iLABS platform as a high-throughput toolkit for cell growth analysis, we evaluated the behavior of iBSC1 cells under varying culture conditions which validated the cross-applicability of HiDef-B8 and indicate its potential for further optimization in livestock-specific stem cell systems.

7. Future Directions

- **Media Optimization:** Investigate synergistic formulations by supplementing HiDef-B8 with livestock-specific growth factors and evaluate HiDef-B8 in longer-term cell culture for cultivated meat stem cells
- **3D Culture Adaptation:** Evaluate how HiDef-B8 performs in scaffold-based or hydrogel-embedded systems.
- **Comparative Species Studies:** Extend experiments to crustacean or seafood satellite cells for broader validation.

8. References

1. Kuo HH, Gao X, DeKeyser JM, Fetterman KA, Pinheiro EA, Weddle CJ, Fonoudi H, Orman MV, Romero-Tejeda M, Jouni M, Blancard M, Magdy T, Epting CL, George AL Jr, Burrige PW. Negligible-Cost and Weekend-Free Chemically Defined Human iPSC Culture. *Stem Cell Reports*. 2020 Feb 11;14(2):256-270. doi: 10.1016/j.stemcr.2019.12.007.
2. Stout, A.J., Mirliani, A.B., Rittenberg, M.L. et al. Simple and effective serum-free medium for sustained expansion of bovine satellite cells for cell cultured meat. *Commun Biol* 5, 466 (2022). doi: 10.1038/s42003-022-03423-8.
3. Stout, A.J., Mirliani, A.B., White, E.C., Yuen, J.S.K., Kaplan, D.L. (2021). Simple and effective serum-free medium for sustained expansion of bovine satellite cells for cell cultured meat. *bioRxiv* preprint. doi:10.1101/2021.05.28.446057
4. Andreishcheva, E.N., Yuen, J.S.K., Parkinson, J., Davidovich, I., Pearce, T.R., Napierala, J.S., Rittenberg, M.L., White, E.C., Kaplan, D.L. (2023). Immortalized bovine satellite cells for cultured meat applications. *ACS Synthetic Biology*, 12(10), 3072-3085. doi:10.1021/acssynbio.3c00216
5. Kumar, A.A., Stout, A.J., Kaplan, D.L. (2023). A Beefy-R culture medium: Replacing albumin with rapeseed protein isolates. *Food Hydrocolloids*, 140, 108592. doi:10.1016/j.foodhyd.2023.108592
6. Tobias Messmer , Iva Klevernic , Carolina Furquim , Ekaterina Ovchinnikova , Arin Dogan , Helder Cruz , Mark J Post , Joshua E Flack. A serum-free media formulation for cultured meat production supports bovine satellite cell differentiation in the absence of serum starvation. NIH <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37118488/>
7. Andrew J. Stout, Xiaoli Zhang, Sophia M. Letcher, Miriam L. Rittenberg, Michelle Shub, Kristin M. Chai, Maya Kaul, David L. Kaplan. Engineered autocrine signaling eliminates

muscle cell FGF2 requirements for cultured meat production. Cell Reports 2024

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